

Influence of Solvent Interaction on the Absorption Spectra of some Phenol Betaines. Part I.

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A series of phenol betaines derived from 4-stilbazoles has been prepared and their absorption spectra have been studied. They show a characteristic charge-transfer absorption band in the visible region which is not shown by the parent conjugated acid in ethanol. This characteristic absorption band undergoes a blue shift in the longer wavelength in the hydroxylic solvents which is attributed to hydrogen bonding. The shift of this characteristic band in polar solvents is in keeping with the nature of charge-transfer absorption band and is in conformity with the dipolar nature of these betaines.

Brooker and Keyes^{1,2} studied the effect of polar solvents on the absorption spectra of the merocyanine dyes with a view to correlate structure with the light absorption. The study is, however, incomplete, as it does not take into account the effect of hydroxylic solvents

1. Brooker and Keyes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5356.
2. Platt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **25**, 80.

on the characteristic charge transfer absorption band. Kosower *et al.*³ studied the absorption spectra of quaternary pyridium iodides in different solvents and the abnormal spectra in the longer wavelength has been attributed to the charge transfer absorption band caused by the ionising power of the solvents. An interesting study of the effect of solvent interaction on the absorption spectra of some phenol betaines has been made by Saxena and Stafford⁴, chiefly those on quinoline series. In the present work the preparation of hydroxy-4-stilbazoles has been undertaken with a view to study the influence of solvent interaction on the absorption spectra of the anhydro-salts derived from them.

Only the betaines I, II and III were found to be stable apparently due to the existence of the pyridone-quinone form. In case of betaine IV such a canonical form is not possible which goes to account for its instability and it rapidly decomposed on removal of the solvent.

These betaines could not be analysed satisfactorily due to their strong tendency for solvation and they could be identified as picrates whose melting points corresponded with those of the picrates of the respective methiodides from which the betaines were generated. The absorption maxima of the betaines in different solvents are recorded in the Tables 1 and 2.

For the sake of comparison with the original quaternary methiodides, their absorption maxima were also recorded at different pH. By this method the absorption maxima of the unstable betaines IV and V could also be studied.

TABLE 1
Absorption maxima of the betaines in different solvents

S.No.	Betaines	SOLVENTS					
		Ethanol		ethanol-Chloroform (1 : 1)		ethanol-benzene (1 : 1)	
1.	N-methyl-2'-hydroxy-4-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydrosalt (I)	385m μ , 3.78*	520m μ , 3.62*	380m μ , 3.64*	530m μ , 3.52*	370m μ , 3.64*	525m μ , 3.54*
2.	N-methyl-4'-hydroxy-4-stilbazolium hydroxide anhydrosalt (II)	—	515m μ , 3.99*	—	500m μ , 4.05*	—	542m μ , 3.07*
3.	N-methyl-4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy-4- stilbazolium hydroxide anhydrosalt (III).	410m μ , 3.24*	560m μ , 3.26*	399m μ , 3.49*	585m μ , 3.65*	420m μ , 3.36*	580m μ , 3.66*

* The values in the parenthesis refer to the log *c*.

3. Kosower, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3253-3270.

4. Saxena, Stafford and Stafford, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1579.

TABLE 2

Absorption maxima of the methiodides

S.No.	The quaternary iodide of	SOLVENTS					
		Ethanol		Alkaline Ethanol		D.M.F.	
1.	I	255m μ , 390m μ	370m μ , 515m μ	380m μ , 595m μ			
		3.77* 4.25*	4.18* 4.14*	4.2* 3.58*			
2.	II	258m μ , 392m μ	270m μ , 515m μ	392m μ , 580m μ			
		4.17* 4.52*	4.01* 4.63*	4.2* 4.06*			
3.	III	260m μ , 413m μ	274m μ , 540m μ	410m μ , 585m μ			
		4.04* 4.26*	3.85* 4.74*	4.37* 4.33*			
4.	IV	340m μ , 352m μ	293m μ , 380-90m μ	—	345m μ		
		4.58* 4.59*	4.21* 4.29*		4.12*		
5.	V	265m μ , 412m μ	275m μ , 395m μ	410m μ , 585m μ			
		4.07* 4.37*	3.85* 4.47*	4.37* 4.33*			
			530m μ				
		4.08*					

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydroxy-4-stilbazoles: 0.02 mole of the appropriate hydroxy-benzaldehyde viz., salicylaldehyde, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde, vanillin and protocatechuic aldehyde was boiled under reflux with 0.02 mole of 4-picoline in presence of 10 mls of acetic anhydride, on an oil bath at 160–170° for a period ranging from 3 to 10 hrs. Afterwards unreacted picoline was distilled off. The cooled reaction mixture was boiled with 20 mls of N/2 hydrochloric acid for 1 hr. and then neutralised with ammonia, when the solid hydroxy-4-stilbazole separated was filtered and washed several times with hot water to remove unreacted picoline and the hydroxybenzaldehyde. The solid was decolourised with activated charcoal and recrystallised from ethanol.

Methiodides of hydroxy-4-stilbazoles: The required amount of the hydroxy-4-stilbazole was dissolved in 1 : 1 AnalaR acetone-methanol mixture and heated under reflux with excess of methyl iodide for 1 to 2 hrs., when the desired methiodide separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of the phenol betaine: The desired methiodide was dissolved in absolute alcohol and the solution was warmed with excess of silver carbonate suspended in the solution, when an intense red solution of the betaine was obtained. The solution was filtered and alcohol was removed under reduced pressure giving as black solid in each case.

The melting points and analyses of the various compounds prepared are given in the following table :

TABLE 3

S.No.	Compound	Time of reflux	Yield	Colour	M.P.	Analysis
1.	2'-hydroxy-4-stilbazole (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO)	10 hours	2.1 gms	yellow	192°	Found C, 79.3; H, 5.6; N, 7.0; Reqd. C, 79.2; H, 5.58; N, 7.1.
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NOI)	1 hour		yellow	218° (reported 218-9°) ⁵	Found I, 37.0; Reqd. I, 37.4.
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₀ OH ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈) Betaine I			yellow black	212° 124°	Found N, 12.5; Reqd. N, 12.73. M.P. of the picrate 211-12°. M.m.p. with above undepressed.
2.	3'-hydroxy-4-stilbazole (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO)	10 hours	2.4 gms	pale yellow	204°	Found C, 79.0; H, 5.3; N, 7.4; Reqd. C, 79.2; H, 5.58; N, 7.1.
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NOI)	2 hours		yellow	241-2°	Found I, 37.1; Reqd. I, 37.46.
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₄)			yellow	210°	Found N, 12.4; Reqd. N, 12.73.
3.	4'-hydroxy-4-stilbazole (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO)	5 hours	2.6 gms	yellow	269-70°	Found C, 79.4; H, 5.3; N, 7.5; Reqd. C, 79.2; H, 5.58; N, 7.1.
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NOI)	1½ hours		yellow	244-45° (reported 244°) ⁶	Found I, 37.1; Reqd. I, 37.46.
	Picrate of the methiodide (C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₄) Betaine II			yellow black	241° 244° (first sweels) (m.p. reported 196°) ⁷	Found N, 12.5; Reqd. N, 12.73. M.P. of the picrate 240°. M.m.p. with above undepressed.
4.	3'-4'-dihydroxy-4-stil- bazole (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂)	5 hours	2.3 gms	yellow	222-23°	Found C, 73.5; H, 5.0, N, 6.7 Reqd. C, 73.2; H, 5.16; N, 6.57.
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NO ₂ I)	1 hour		yellow	262°	Found I, 35.3; Reqd. I, 35.76.
	Picrate of the methio- dide (C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₉ N ₄)			dirty yellow	176°	Found N, 12.6; Reqd. N, 12.28.
5.	4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy- 4-stilbazole (C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂)	3 hours	2.4 gms	dirty yellow	192°	Found C, 73.9; H, 5.6; N, 6.3; Reqd. C, 74.0; H, 5.7; N, 6.16.
	Methiodide of the above (C ₁₅ H ₁₆ NO ₂ I)	1 hour		yellow	254° (Reported 254°) ⁸	Found I, 34.0 Reqd. I, 34.4.
	Picrate of the methio- dide (C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₉ N)			yellowish orange	181°	Found N, 11.5; Reqd. N, 11.91.
	Betaine III			black	252-4°	M.P. of the picrate 180°. M.m.p. with above undepressed.

5. Phillips, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, **12**, 333.

6. Takahshi, Satake and Yasui, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1954, **74**, 1212.

7. Lippert and Mor, *Z. Electro. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 718.

DISCUSSION

The study of the absorption maxima of the betaines I, II and III (Table 1) shows the appearance of a characteristic absorption band in the visible region, which is not present in the spectra of the respective methiodides in ethanol (Table 2). This band is attributed to the characteristic charge transfer band as shown by its susceptibility to the solvent interaction. Thus in a more polar 1 : 1 ethanol-chloroform medium, a bathochromic shift of this band is observed. The same effect is observed in 1 : 1 ethanol benzene mixture (effect of benzene as a non-polar solvent). The spectra of the betaines in chloroform or benzene separately could not be recorded as they are insoluble in them.

The spectra of the betaines IV and V were studied through their methiodides in alkaline ethanol and D.M.F. (Table 2), as they were unstable and could not be obtained in crystalline form. In each case, a bathochromic shift of charge transfer absorption band in the longer wavelength is observed in the more polar solvent. The hypsochromic shift of the absorption band in ethanol is attributed to hydrogen bonding.

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